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ENFORCEMENT & RURAL ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT VOE - BUMDes (VILLAGE- OWNED ENTERPRISES)

Ade Isyana Hairunnisa¹, Erlina², Sirojuzilam³, Rujiman⁴
Regional Planning - Postgraduate, Universitas Sumatera Utara

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Abstract

Purpose - This research is investigate fundamental factor of that influence village economic development based on Village-Owned Enterprises [VOE] or (BUMDes) by investigating the relationship between the influence of capital participation, human resources, governance, and rural area planning on the development of the village-economy based on VOE in the Regency/City of North Sumatera Province.

Design/methodology/approach - The study approach employed is quantitative survey research, in which data is collected from a population sample that is meant to reflect the entire population. A research questionnaire was distributed to the entire population, fifty-three BUMDes in North Sumatera. Five hundred twelve questionnaires were distributed, with nine respondents for each BUMDes, and four hundred ninety-eight were returned. After processing the data with multivariate statistics analysis, the research shows that human resources, capital participation, governance, and regional planning all have a small impact on the growth of the BUMDes-based village economy.

Research limitations/implications - In multivariate analysis, the structural model is evaluated using the R-square for the dependent variable and the path coefficient for the independent variable, then tested for significance using the t-statistic value for each path. Thus, Y equals $0,147 X1 + 0,165 X2 + 0,319 X3 + 0,153 X4$.

Originality/value - Village fund allocation is a stimulant to finance and encourage village government programs based on community self-help, mutual collaboration, and community empowerment. And the study found that human resources, capital participation, governance, and regional planning all contribute to the development of VOE-based village economies.

Keyword : Village-Owned Enterprises (BUMDes), multivariate analysis, rural planning, North Sumatera

Paper Type : Research paper

Introduction

A country's development might aim to improve three things: the availability and distribution of necessities; people's living standards; and their ability to access economic and social activities (Todaro, 2004). From 2013 to 2015, the Indonesian economy grew less, with a

minor increase from 2016 to 2018. From 2019 to 2020, the downturn resumed. A country's development can aim to improve three things: the availability and distribution of necessities, the level of living, and the community's ability to engage in both economic and social activities (Todaro, 2004). From 2013 to 2015, Indonesia's economic growth slowed but increased slightly from 2016 to 2018. From 2019 to 2020, the downturn resumed. Villages currently have inadequate economic development, high poverty, and unemployment rates and are less competitive than cities. According to the Central Bureau of Statistics, there were two poor individuals in 2013: urban (8.52%) and rural (14.42%). The government has adopted a national development policy that prioritizes village development to address these issues. Village development is important in national and regional development because it promotes equitable development and directly benefits the majority of rural dwellers. Villages have enormous population and natural resource potential. If these two potentials are managed well, the villages will benefit.

One of the policies enacted alongside Law No. 6 of 2014 was Government Regulation No. 60 of 2014. The Village Law and Government Regulation No. 60/2014 on Village Funds give villages new tools to develop themselves. To develop BUMDes (Village-Owned Enterprises) or VOE as a firm basis for the people's welfare, the government has started to enhance and prioritize using village funds to establish VOE as economic actors who manage village potential collectively to promote village residents' welfare.

Villages must start managing village assets owned through VOE, which were developed based on potential village characteristics and the needs of inhabitants. The development of VOE in North Sumatera began in 2015 with local fund circulation. In 2018, 53 VOE from 159 villages were mapped in North Sumatera Regency/City. Villagers in North Sumatera Regency and City rely on agriculture for their livelihood. Farmers still work on rice fields by hand and lack information and understanding about technological advancements, particularly agricultural technology. The village government continues to assist in addressing all communal issues. Along with community leaders and representatives, the Village Government holds debates based on the Minister of Villages, Development of Disadvantaged Areas, and Transmigration Regulation No. 4 of 2015.

Literature review

Human Resources

Human Resources (HR) is a planning, implementation, and maintenance strategy that tries to manage people (workers) to maximize business performance, including developing policies and processes to support the strategy. They define HR as establishing various formal procedures within an organization to ensure the effective and efficient use of human knowledge to achieve targeted organizational or company goals.

Capital Participation

Light (2004) cites Bordieu (1986) for the contribution of human, cultural, and social capital. In line with the investment principle, these three types of additional capital can be created and developed to reap the rewards. Human capital is described as individual knowledge and abilities. In contrast, *cultural capital* is cultural knowledge that helps society, and social capital is defined as trust relationships rooted in social networks. According to Gaag (2005), social capital is a model of economic activity based on social interactions. Gaag (2005) sees this as a fundamental understanding of social capital. This process is enabled by reciprocity, trust, complementarity, and supportive norms.

Village Administration

According to Article 23 of the UUDes, village governance is run by the village government. The village apparatus assists the village head (Article 25 UUDes jo Article 1 number 3 PP No. 43/2014). Each regional administration might use a different name for the village head and local apparatus.

Planning theory regional planning is a development planning process meant to improve a community, government, and environment by utilizing existing resources. It must be positive, thorough, and adhere to the priority concept (Riyadi & Bratakusumah, 2003). The process of economic growth and fair development is the most significant topic that

economists and regional planners are concerned about. The difference between regional and national economic growth theories is openness in the input-output process of products, services, and people. The regional system allows for more free movement of people, products, and services than the national system (Sirojuzilam, 2007).

Research methods

The research method utilized is legal and social research or empirical legal research (non-doctrinal research). The study approach employed is quantitative survey research, in which data is collected from a population sample that is meant to reflect the entire population. A research questionnaire was distributed to the entire population, fifty-three BUMDes in North Sumatera. Five hundred twelve questionnaires were distributed, with nine respondents for each BUMDes, and four hundred ninety-eight were returned. After processing the data with multivariate statistics analysis, the research shows that human resources, capital participation, governance, and regional planning all have a small impact on the growth of the BUMDes-based village economy. This study's SEM method is the MLE (Maximum Likelihood Estimator) method. According to Hair et al. in Ferdinand (2002), the sample size required using this method is between 200-500 samples with the conditions of normality met. This study will explore the causal relationship between exogenous and endogenous variables, both endogenous intervening and endogenous dependent, and the research instrument's validity and reliability. Thus, SEM analysis uses the AMOS (Analysis of Moment Structure) version 21 and SPSS version 20 software tools. AMOS program 21 uses multiple variable analysis with structural equation modeling (SEM) to test the hypothesis. The proposed hypothesis is tested by comparing the probability value (p) to the alpha (0.05) significant level. The hypothesis is accepted if the probability (p) is less than alpha (0.05). The hypothesis is rejected if the probability value (p) is more significant than (0.05). But first, confirmatory factor analysis is performed to determine whether indications are legitimate and may be used to establish a factor or construct. The next step is to convert the theory-based model into a path diagram to be estimated using the AMOS 21 tool. A structural model has two variables: exogenous and endogenous. The structural equations express the causation link between distinct structures and variables. The equation is built using the following rules:

$$\text{Endogenous variables (dependent)} = \text{exogenous variables} + \text{endogenous variables} + \text{error}$$

(Ferdinand, 2002: 167).

Exogenous variables, like independent variables and instrument variables, are decided outside the model (also called predetermined variables). Endogenous variables, like dependent variables, are decided by the model. The standard assumptions in SEM analysis include Chi-square, Significance Probability, RMSEA (Root Mean Square Error of Approximation), GFI (Goodness of Fit Index), AGFI (Adjusted GFI), CMIN/DF (Normed Chi-Square), TLI (Tucker- Lewis Index), and CFI (Comparative Fit Index). This study's structural equation is recursive and meets the following assumptions. 3. The causal influence of endogenous variables is unidirectional, or none has a reciprocal (reciprocal) effect. The structural model equation is created in this study to determine the causal relationship between the variables. The conceptual research model proposes structural equations as follows:

No	Structural Equation
1	$Y = \gamma + \beta X + \varepsilon$
2	$Y = \gamma + \beta_1 Y_1 + \beta_2 Y_2 + \beta_3 Y_3 + \beta_4 Y_4 + \varepsilon_1$

Table 1.
Random
criteria

β = (betha) the path coefficient of the exogenous variable (Z); γ = (gamma) the path coefficient of the intervening variable (Z); Y = Regional Planning; X_1 = HR; X_2 = Institutional; X_3 = Management, X_4 = Sustainability and ε = error.

Result

In Indonesia, the governor is a regional chief who represents the central government in the regions. This role involves bridging and shortening the extent of jurisdiction over government tasks and operations, including establishing and monitoring some local government administrations in districts and cities (Hadiwijoyo, 2011: 64). The central

government delegating authority to the governor is an example of de-concentration in Indonesia. Deconcentration is defined in the UUPD (Regional Regulation Law) as the transfer of a portion of central government jurisdiction to the governor, vertical agencies in certain areas, and/or the governor and the regent/mayor as the person in charge. gov affairs Article 91 of the UUPD makes this clear. According to the study, only one regency (North Tapanuli) has local regulations, namely Mandailing Natal Regency. A Perda that regulates the establishment of FKAKD should be issued by the District/City Government officials of North Sumatra Province, according to the Van Meter and Van Horn policy implementation theory (Agustino, 2006: 139). (laws and regulations). Adoption of Following the presentation of descriptive data, data analysis can be categorized by regions/districts to provide an early description of the implementation aspects of synergy between village heads and BPD. The data distribution by % is shown below the table of seventeen parameters. This table shows the overall synergy between village leaders and BPD in North Sumatra:

Apparatus Village	Education (%)						Profession (%)				
	SD	SMP	SMU	D1-D3	S1	S2-S3	PNS/ TNI/POLRI	Private	Entrep reneur	Others	
BPD	6	17	57	4	15	1	2	9	25	64	
Village head	0	7	67	6	19	1	6	0	13	81	
Public	21	23	48	3	5	0	2	3	45	49	

Table 2.
Education
of
Apparatus
Village

Village chiefs and BPD in North Sumatra are 47 and 51 years old, respectively. Local government programs rely on regeneration and leadership to be successful. Village heads in SU Province were 85% male and 13% female, while BPD was 90% male and 9% female. Five parameters measure institutional synergy in implementing regional administration.

Parameter	KD (%)					BPD (%)					Public				
	SB	B	R	KB	TB	SB	B	R	KB	TB	SB	B	R	KB	TB
Planning	11	87	2	0	0	21	68	9	2	0	15	71	14	1	0
Implementation	6	89	6	0	0	15	72	9	4	0	7	76	16	1	0
Post-Program & Communication	17	83	0	0	0	23	64	11	2	0	11	68	21	0	0

Table 3.
Village
Officials
Distribution
of Synergy

*) SB = Very Good; B = Good; R = Doubt; KB = Poorly dan TB = Not Good

At the planning stage, the planning referred to is related to the formulation of village regulations, the preparation of the village medium term development plan, the preparation of village development programs. From the research results, it was found that as many as 87% of village heads and 68% of BPD members were involved in the planning stages of drafting village regulations, RPJMDes, and village development programs. The involvement of BPD members in the implementation of village government programs is the formulation of village government development program planning and community development. Considerations of community needs were obtained through hamlet meetings, community aspirations related to village development, namely physical development, and especially the prevention and mitigation of the direct or indirect impact of the Covid-19 outbreak. At the implementation stage the involvement of the Village Head was 89% and the BPD was 72%. The variables to be tested are the Y = Regional Planning; X₁ = HR; X₂ = Institutional; X₃ = Management and X₄= Sustainability with the following results.

Effect between variables	Standardized Estimate	S.E.	P	Sig.	
(Y) ← (X1)	0,147	0,050	***	S**	Table 2. Variables' effects Y
(Y) ← (X2)	0,165	0,048	***	S**	
(Y) ← (X3)	0,319	0,055	***	S**	
(Y) ← (X4)	0,153	0,058	***	S**	

Discussions and implications

In a quantitative study, the researchers concluded that human resources were an important factor influencing the growth of the VOE-based village economy. The t-statistic is bigger than the t-table in this study, indicating that the four variables substantially affect the growth of the VOE-based village economy. VOE is an autonomous business-capital economic institution established on community initiative. VOE business units can use local resources and technology such as a) village drinking water; b) village electricity; c) food barns, and other appropriate technologies, according to Permendesa No. 4 of 2015. The community must provide VOE business financing. However, VOE can request capital loans from outside parties, such as the village government. It follows the law (Law No. 32 of 2004 concerning Regional Government, Article 213 paragraph 3).

The Constitution's Article 55 and Permendagri No. 110/2016's Article 31 relate to one of the initial BPD functions, namely discussing and agreeing on a draft village regulation with the village head. As demonstrated above, the SEM calculation results indicate that all variables and indicators have a substantial effect. However, HR (X₁), shows that activities are harmful to the study objectives. Village leaders and BPD have disagreements over budgets, hamlet head appointments, road development priorities, development planning discussions, project implementer supervision, and material price issues described in RAB and RKP oversight. Conflicts between the BPD and the village head frequently emerge due to members encouraging the BPD chair and the village head to be antagonistic. However, adhering to the mandate of government rules in convening village meetings, according to Article 38 Permendagri No. 110/2016, the results of monitoring the village head's performance are included in the BPD performance report. As a result of policy study and case analysis, the Protected Village model generates the following flow of formulations:

Pandemic COVID-19 (X) → VOE (Z) → Management VOE (X3) → Village Recovery & Preparedness Program (X2) → Sustainability (X4) → Human Resources (X1).

Capital is a major determinant of VOE' success. Business, human, and social capital are all required to build VOE. The success of VOE will impact the rural economy. The role of capital participation in village economic growth on Java's island needs study because numerous VOE, especially VOE, continue to flourish and produce village economic growth. The SEM findings reveal that all variables and indicators are significant. The positive path coefficient shows that the X₁ = HR; X₂ = Institutional; X₃ = Management and X₄= Sustainability has a substantial and beneficial effect.

Conclusion

Based on the identified issues and research findings, it can be stated that:

1. The Human Resources variable partially influences the VOE-based village economy. It indicates that as human resources grow, so does the village economy. VOE' motivation, comfort, initiative, managerial capability, and comprehension are human resource indicators. Based on VOE, all these factors considerably impact village economic growth.
2. Equity participation has a substantial impact on VOE-based village economies. Village government support for village fund allocation are measures of capital participation. Based on VOE, all these factors considerably impact village economic growth.
3. The governance variable has a considerable effect on the village economy, according to VOE. Accounting, performance evaluation, and financial responsibility are examples of governance indicators.
4. The regional planning variable influences the VOE -based village economy. Economic, social, and institutional indicators of rural area planning Based on VOE, all these factors considerably impact village economic growth.

From the discussion analysis, the following conclusions and restrictions can be inferred: Furthermore, the research area should cover not only the Regency/City of North Sumatera but also other locations, such as Northern Sumatera, which comprises the Provinces of Aceh and North Sumatera.

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Corresponding authors & co-authors

Ade Isyana Hairunnisah, SE., Ak., M.Ak., CA. can be contacted at: isyana.hairunnisah@gmail.com
 Prof. Erlina, SE., Ak., M.Ak., CA. can be contacted at: erlina@usu.ac.id